

Received 23 December 2022, accepted 3 January 2023, date of publication 5 January 2023, date of current version 10 January 2023.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3234501

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Deep Learning Receiver for Non-Linear Transmitter

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This work was supported by the European Commission through the H2020 Project Hexa-X under Agreement 101015956.

ABSTRACT Non-linearity of wireless transceivers, specifically power amplifier (PA) non-linearity, could pose major limitations towards having high throughput, and cost and energy efficient wireless communication systems. Such limitations from the PA is typically compensated in the transmitter, e.g. by applying power back-off or performing digital-pre-distortion (DPD) aiming to linearize the transmitter. However, applying PA power back-off leads to lower energy efficiency, and lower output power, and hence lower coverage; and performing DPD results in higher complexity of the transmitters. This paper presents an alternative approach based on a receiver method to perform signal detection in the presence of distortions due to PA non-linearity. We propose a receiver technique using artificial neural networks (ANN) to compensate for the PA non-linearity at the receiver side. The paper presents link-level simulation results using pre-trained neural network models based on synthesized training data. The simulation results confirm that the designed receiver can tolerate higher distortions, hence allow the PA output power back-off to be reduced, leading to higher output power improving coverage, spectral efficiency, energy efficiency, and throughput.

INDEX TERMS Machine learning, artificial intelligence, artificial neural networks, 6G, power amplifier.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 6G radio cellular networks are envisioned to provide increased throughput for wireless signal transmission compared to their 5G counterparts while maintaining network energy consumption and hardware cost at sustainable levels.

However, reliable signal transmission in the presence of hardware impairments in radio frequency (RF) transceivers, e.g. oscillator phase noise, power amplifier (PA) non-linearity, and digital-to-analog converter (DAC) quantization noise would be even more challenging compared to 5G. On the one hand, 6G is expected to provide extreme throughput by wide-band transmission at higher frequency bands, e.g. sub-THz, on the other hand, at higher carrier frequencies, there is stronger phase noise, the output power and the energy efficiency of PAs are lower, and the design of high-resolution DAC is more challenging. Hence, techniques would be required to compensate the impact of RF hardware impairments and enable reliable communication in

the presence of RF transceivers that operate under extreme conditions.

The power amplifier is usually considered the most power demanding device in a wireless transceiver, hence, improvements in the energy efficiency of PAs are directly reflected in the overall energy efficiency of the radio transceivers [1]. To extend the coverage and enhance the energy efficiency of radio networks, it is desired to operate power amplifiers in a regime that maximizes the achievable output power, and improves energy efficiency. This implies PA operation in a more non-linear regime compared to the current operation regime. However, in such operation regime the induced distortions due to non-linearity degrades the quality of the communication link and makes signal reception at receivers more challenging. To mitigate the impact of distortions and improve throughput, a wide range of solutions have been applied at the transmitter side to linearize transmitter and reduce the impact of associated distortions. PA circuit design using III-V technology, e.g. GaAs, or GaN technologies, instead of CMOS technology and new PA design architectures [2], [3] can achieve higher dynamic range, but at a relatively higher cost. Applying *power back-off* has been

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Chen Chen¹.

a common approach to mitigate PA non-linearity and set the PA operating point in a more linear regime, degrading energy efficiency and reducing output power. *Digital-pre-distortion (DPD)* is another technique which applies inverse distortion using a pre-distorter before feeding the signal to the PA, targeting an overall linear RF transmitter. This typically requires an accurate estimation of PA non-linearity characteristics using a feedback loop from the PA's output signal and extensive signal processing at the transmitter's baseband unit. The signal processing for DPD for wideband signals at high-band is even more complex and power-hungry [4]. In addition, in uplink (UL) communication scenarios, for a user equipment (UE) or a mobile device with limited computational capability, it is challenging or even infeasible to perform DPD. *Peek to average power ratio (PAPR) reduction techniques* have been proposed in the literature to reduce the signal's PAPR allowing a more efficient operating region of the PA. These techniques achieve lower PAPR at the cost of increased bit-error-rate (BER), reduced throughput, or higher complexity [5], [6]. *Waveform design* to aim for generating signals that allow more efficient PA operation is another approach which has been extensively investigated [7], [8]. This aims at designing waveform that generate signal with lower PAPR, hence, are less sensitive to the distortions due to PA non-linearity. However, the waveforms with relatively lower PAPR usually require larger bandwidth.

The aforementioned techniques mainly aim to linearize the transmitter, so that the receiver can treat the residual distortions as noise and perform signal detection. The legacy receivers are usually designed based on the assumption that the receiver noise has Gaussian uncorrelated distribution. However, the distortions due to transceiver non-linearity would cause the receiver to deviate from these assumptions and operate sub-optimally. It has been shown that non-linearity at the transmitter side in multicarrier transmissions can lead to performance gain given that an optimum detector is used at the receiver side [9], [10], [11]. Iterative frequency domain equalization (FDE) such as iterative block decision-feedback equalizer (IB-DFE) can be used to perform signal detection in the presence of imperfections, e.g. for modulated signals with single-carrier frequency domain equalization (SC-FDE) [12].

A *new design paradigm* is to skip linearization techniques at the transmitter or to perform limited linearization, transmitting a distorted signal. Instead, a non-linear receiver that can detect signals in the presence of distortions is designed. An iterative method for maximum likelihood detection of multi-carrier symbols in the presence of PA non-linearity is proposed in [13]. A method for digital post distortion (DPoD) of the signal that performs signal detection by reconstructing the distorted signal is proposed in [14] and [15]. These methods require PA non-linearity model parameters to be known at receiver. In [16], a model identification method is proposed for PA non-linearity estimation at receiver, embedded in an iterative decision-based scheme, to compensate the impact of non-linearity. For PA non-linearity compensation in multi-

user transmission, a receiver technique for joint cancellation of non-linearity is proposed in [17], and a receiver method for successive cancellation of distortion is proposed in [18]. A method for signal detection of single-carrier high-order QAM modulated signal is proposed in [19]. This method quantizes the received signal and uses a lookup table to perform demapping of the distorted signal.

Machine learning techniques, provide an opportunity to learn the receivers that can handle signal detection in the presence of distortions. A context-aware receiver based on *artificial neural networks (ANN)* is proposed in [20]. This receiver learns the optimized demapper to compensate the impact of oscillator phase noise. A receiver method based on convolutional neural networks (CNN) for processing in time and frequency domains for CP-OFDM waveform subject to PA non-linearity is proposed in [21]. The method is based on joint processing using neural network for demapping, equalization, and channel estimation in frequency domain, and a time-domain filter to compensate the impact of distortions due to PA non-linearity, and performance gains in terms of bit error rate (BER) are shown.

In this paper, we propose a neural network empowered receiver to compensate the impact of PA non-linearity for DFT-s-OFDM transmitted signals. The proposed method performs only demapping for each modulated symbol while the other receiver functionalities can be performed as part of the legacy receiver. This significantly reduces the overall complexity of the AI/ML-based solution. We evaluated the performance of the proposed method using link level simulations in terms of un-coded bit error rate (BER), block error rate (BLER), and throughput, and measured the spectral emission at the operating point of the system. Also, we evaluated the energy efficiency of the proposed method in terms of power added efficiency (PAE) of the PA. We compared the performance of the proposed method against a legacy receiver. The simulation results confirm that the proposed method can increase throughput and/or extend the coverage of a communication link, and enhance energy efficiency in the presence of PA non-linearity.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the studied system model. Section III describes the considered PA model for simulations in this paper. Section IV presents the proposed receiver architecture, the considered neural network, and the training of the neural network. Section V shows the simulation results. Section VI discusses the network operation to integrate the proposed method and the benefits of the proposed method in downlink and uplink scenarios. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This paper considers a DFT-s-OFDM signal transmission in the presence of PA non-linearity. The schematic diagram of the considered transmitter is shown in Fig. 1. In the considered transmitter, information bits are encoded using LDPC codes with rate r , and the encoded bits are mapped to symbols in an M -ary QAM modulator. A discrete Fourier

FIGURE 1. Transmitter architecture.

FIGURE 2. The constellations of the received and equalized signals for 16QAM modulated signal and DFT-s-OFDM waveform for a transmitter with linear PA.

transformation (DFT) is applied to the modulated signals, and orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) scheme is performed on the resulting signal. The DFT-s-OFDM modulated signals are sent through an RF chain which is subject to PA non-linearity. In this paper, other RF hardware components are assumed to be ideal to investigate the impact of PA non-linearity. The considered PA model is presented in the following section.

III. POWER AMPLIFIER MODEL

A memory-less polynomial model is used in this paper to model PA non-linearity at the transmitter. The PA's non-linearity is modeled as follows

$$y_p(n) = \sum_{k \in K_p} a_k x(n) |x(n)|^{2k}, \quad (1)$$

where n is the time index, $x(n)$ is the PA's input, $y_p(n)$ is the PA's output, a_k is the k th order polynomial coefficient, and K_p is the set of polynomial orders that are considered in the model. PA model parameters for CMOS and GaN technologies which are computed based on measurements are specified in [22]. In this paper, numerical evaluations are performed based on PA model for GaN technology.

The constellation of the received signals for 16QAM modulated signal and DFT-s-OFDM waveform for the cases with linear PA is shown in Fig. 2, and for the case with non-linear PA and 2dB back-off is shown in Fig. 3. It can

FIGURE 3. The constellations of the received and equalized signals for 16QAM modulated signal and DFT-s-OFDM waveform for a transmitter with non-linear PA with 4dB back-off.

be seen that in the case of linear PA, the received symbols are distorted with uncorrelated Gaussian noise, however, in the presence of PA non-linearity the distribution of the noise deviates from uncorrelated Gaussian and the constellation diagram compresses towards the origin. This implies that the legacy receivers that rely on the assumption of uncorrelated Gaussian noise would not be optimal under these conditions. In the following section, we propose a receiver that learns the optimal signal detection in the presence of distortions.

IV. RECEIVER ARCHITECTURE

The designed AI-empowered receiver architecture for distorted DFT-s-OFDM modulated signals is shown in Fig. 4. The receiver performs channel estimation using reference signals, and conducts equalization of the received signal using the estimated channel state information (CSI). A neural network demapper is designed to receive equalized symbols and SNR estimate to compute log likelihood ratios (LLR) or soft bits. The computed soft bits are used as inputs to an LDPC decoder. The neural network demapper's architecture and the training of the neural network model is described in the following sections.

1) NEURAL NETWORK DEMAPPER'S ARCHITECTURE

A fully connected neural network (FCNN) [23] is used for per symbol-based soft bit demapping of the received signals.

FIGURE 4. AI-empowered receiver architecture.

TABLE 1. The neural network specification.

Parameter	Setting
Number of input neurons	3
Number of output neurons	$\log_2(M)$
Number of hidden layers	5
Number of neurons in each hidden layer	64
The activation function of the hidden layers	ReLU
The activation function of the output layer	Linear
Number of model parameters	50K

The FCNN is applied for processing at each resource element, where the inputs of the FCNN are the real and imaginary part of the equalized received symbol and the SNR estimate, and the outputs are the LLR values corresponding to the transmitted coded bits. The assumptions regarding the FCNN architecture are summarized in Table 1.

2) NEURAL NETWORK DEMAPPER’S TRAINING

The training of the neural network can be performed based on training data from measurements or from simulators. The training data includes *features* which are equalized symbols, SNR estimate computed by the equalizer over each DFT-s-OFDM symbol, and *labels* which are the corresponding transmitted bits. In this paper, the neural networks are trained using synthetic data generated from link simulators with several configurations including PA back-off value, the case with linear PA, and multiple SNR values.

The *loss function* which is used for model training is *binary cross entropy* defined as follows

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{i=1}^{\log_2(M)} \left(b_{i,j} \log_2(\hat{b}_{i,j}) + (1 - b_{i,j}) \log_2(1 - \hat{b}_{i,j}) \right), \tag{2}$$

where $|\mathcal{B}|$ is the batch size, $b_{i,j}$ is the i th bit of the j th transmitted symbol in the batch, and $\hat{b}_{i,j}$ is the corresponding likelihood value.

The model is trained using *Adam* optimizer algorithm [24]. The learning rate and the mini-batch size are the main hyper-parameters that are selected from a set of candidates. The input features are normalized to zero mean and unit variance quantities, where the normalization coefficients are computed based on the statistics of the data set. The assumptions regarding the training of the FCNN are listed in Table 2.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present evaluation results based on link simulations to compare the performance of the proposed

TABLE 2. The neural network training parameters.

Parameter	Setting
Number of training samples	0.5M
Optimizer	Adam
Mini-batch size	1024
Learning rate	0.0001
Number of epochs	10

TABLE 3. Simulation assumptions for training and validation.

Parameter	Training	Validation	Randomization
Waveform	DFT-s-OFDM		None
Transmitter’s IDFT size (N)	1024		None
Transmitter’s IDFT size (M)	624		None
Modulation	64QAM, 256QAM		None
PA backoff	4dB		None
SNR	0dB - 30dB		Uniform
Carrier frequency	3.5 GHz		None
Sub-carrier spacing	15 KHz		None
Bandwidth	10 MHz		None
Channel model	TDL-A		None
UE speed	3 km/h		None
RMS delay spread	100 nsec		None
HARQ re-transmissions	None	3	None
MCS Table	Table 5.1.3.1-2. in [25]		None

NN-empowered receiver against a legacy receiver with conventional demapper in the presence of PA non-linearity and the legacy receiver in the presence of linear PA. The simulation assumptions for data collection for training neural network model and for performance evaluation of the methods are summarized in Table 3. The performance metrics that are considered for the evaluations include uncoded bit error rate (BER), block error rate (BLER), power added efficiency (PAE), and throughput. In the figures presented in this section, the black curves marked with circles are corresponding to the legacy receiver in the presence of linear PA, the red curves marked with squares are corresponding to the legacy receiver in the presence of non-linear PA, and the blue curves marked with rectangles are corresponding to the proposed receiver with NN-demapper.

Fig. 5 shows the power spectral density (PSD) of the transmitted signal from a transmitter with a GaN PA for different values of PA back-off values. It also shows the spectrum emission mask (SEM) specified by 3GPP standard [26] that the transmitted signals need to comply with to fulfill the requirements on the out of band (OOB) emissions. It can be seen that the transmitted signal from a PA with 4dB back-off generates OOB emissions that meet the requirements. Hence, it can be considered as an operating point of the system. At this operating point, the measured error vector magnitude

FIGURE 5. Power spectral density for different power amplifier back-off values, and spectral emission limit (SEM).

FIGURE 6. BER performance of the NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for 64QAM signal.

FIGURE 7. BER performance of the NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for 256QAM signal.

(EVM), the in-band distortion measure, is 7.2%; and the measured adjacent carrier leakage ratio (ACLR), the OOB emission measure, is 29.6 dB. In the presented evaluations, PA with 4dB power back-off is used to investigate the proposed technique in the presence of inband distortions due to PA non-linearity.

FIGURE 8. BLER performance of the NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for 64QAM signal coded with MCS=19.

FIGURE 9. BLER performance of the NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for 64QAM signal coded with MCS=27.

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the raw BER performance for 64QAM and 256QAM modulated signals, respectively. In the simulations, to compute BER, the error events are detected by comparing the sign of the computed soft bits and transmitted bits. Hence, the impact of error correcting decoder is not reflected in these results. The legacy receiver having a linear PA can be considered as a lower bound for BER performance. It can be seen that the NN-demapper outperforms the legacy demapper and the performance gain is larger at higher SNR regime, where PA non-linearity has more severe impact on receiver’s performance degradation.

Fig. 8 shows BLER performance of the considered methods for 64QAM modulated signals with MCS index 19 [25]. Comparing the BLER performance of the legacy demapper in the presence of PA non-linearity, and that of the proposed receiver with NN-demapper, it can be seen that, at 10% BLER which is a reasonable operating point, the proposed method reaches roughly 1dB performance gain.

The BLER performance of the considered methods for 64QAM modulated signals with MCS index 27 is shown in Fig. 9. Compared to the simulation scenario for Fig. 8, the code rate is higher with the error correcting code providing less protection against errors. For this setting, the

FIGURE 10. BLER performance of the NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for 256QAM signal coded with MCS=20.

FIGURE 11. Achievable throughput with adaptive modulation order and coding rate and with NN-based receiver and legacy receiver for modulation orders up to 64QAM.

legacy receiver can not successfully detect the signals and fails to reach 10% BLER, while the proposed receiver with NN-demapper still can perform signal detection in the presence of PA non-linearity. Hence, the proposed receiver enables selecting an MCS with higher code rate while signal reception with the desired reliability is still feasible.

Fig. 10 shows the BLER performance of the studied methods for 256QAM modulated signals. The evaluations are performed for the MCS index 20 which is corresponding to the lowest code rate for this modulation order according to Table 5.1.3.1-2. in 3GPP specifications [25]. For this modulation scheme even for the lowest code rate defined, the legacy receiver can not successfully detect the signals and fails to reach 10% BLER. However, the proposed receiver with NN-demapper can provide satisfactory results without any visible error-floor. This confirms that the proposed receiver can enable using higher order modulations while providing signal reception with desired reliability.

The achievable throughput of the considered methods in the presence of link adaptation is shown in Fig. 11. In the simulations, the link adaptation is performed by selecting the highest MCS index, corresponding to the modulation order and the code rate, for which the received signals can reach

FIGURE 12. Power added efficiency for different power back-off values.

the target block error rate of typically 10%. The highest modulation order that was considered in the simulations with link adaptation was 64QAM. The legacy receiver in the presence of linear PA provides an upper bound on the achievable throughput. In the presence of PA non-linearity, the legacy receiver achieves lower throughput compared to the upper bound, and the performance gap become larger at higher SNR values. At high SNR regime, the throughput saturates at a lower level compared to the one that can be achieved when there is no PA non-linearity. The proposed receiver with NN-demapper achieves higher throughput compared with legacy receiver. The performance gain is larger at higher SNR values and the achieved throughput saturates at the same level as the one for the upper bound on throughput.

To quantify the energy efficiency improvements, PAE for different back-off values is shown in Fig. 12. It can be seen that increasing the back-off value degrades the efficiency of the PA. Since the proposed method enables operation with lower back-off values while achieving similar performance as the legacy receiver, the energy efficiency of the power amplifier can be improved. In the presence of non-linear PA, with 10dB back-off, the legacy receiver can achieve almost similar performance as the one with linear PA. Considering this, it can be inferred from Fig. 11 that the NN-based receiver with 4dB back-off at transmitter can achieve similar performance as the legacy receiver with 10dB back-off. Therefore, according to the results in Fig. 11 the PAE can be improved roughly 70%.

The results based on our performance evaluations are summarized in Table 4 and can have different interpretations as outlined in the following. The performance evaluations in terms of BLER versus SNR confirms that for a given SNR value, the NN-empowered receiver requires lower number of re-transmissions. Hence, for a given scheduling strategy, the network with NN-empowered receivers will have a higher success rate for transmission of information blocks and hence can achieve higher capacity compared to the one with legacy receivers. It also confirms that for a given SNR value, a lower

TABLE 4. Performance gain summary.

	Bit error rate (BER) gain	Block error rate (BLER) gain			Throughput gain		Power added efficiency (PAE) gain
		MCS=19	MCS=27	MCS=20	@ 25dB	@ 30dB	
64 QAM	4dB @ 1%BER	1dB	NOTE1	-	12%	17%	70%
256 QAM	2dB @ 4%BER	-	-	NOTE1	NOTE2	NOTE2	NOTE3
NOTE1: Baseline fails to reach 10% BLER while NN-empower receiver's performance is stable.							
NOTE2: Full throughput envelope not simulated for indicated modulation.							
NOTE3: Power added efficiency not measured for indicated modulation.							

BLER and hence higher reliability can be achieved with NN-empowered receivers. It can be observed that in certain cases, e.g., 256 QAM, the legacy receiver cannot establish relatively reliable link (e.g., the one with 10% BLER), while the NN-empowered receiver can provide the possibility for transmission with 10% BLER. The throughput versus SNR performance evaluations confirm that the NN-empowered receiver can enhance spectral efficiency of a communication link. In addition, the throughput versus SNR performance evaluations confirm that to reach a given throughput, lower SNR is required with the NN-empowered receiver compared to the legacy receiver, hence, the link budget can be improved. This implies that enhanced coverage can be achieved with the NN-empowered receiver. The performance evaluations in terms of PAE confirm that the proposed method can improve the energy efficiency of the transmitter by enabling the transmitter to reduce PA backoff and hence operate with higher energy efficiency while the proposed method can compensate distortions at the receiver side.

The NN-empowered receiver compared to the benchmark receiver requires extra processing. The neural network needs to be trained based on measured or synthetic training data and when the model is trained, it can be used for inference. The training requires extensive processing, but it can be performed once, and it may need to be occasionally re-trained only if it is needed. The inference has higher complexity compared to the benchmark method; hence, the method requires relatively more capable hardware at the receiver side and higher energy consumption for digital processing at the receiver. This implies that the method would be more suitable for uplink scenarios, where the base station side has a more capable receiver compared to the user equipment and has limited constraint on energy consumption.

VI. NETWORK OPERATION OF NN-RECEIVER

The proposed NN-empowered receiver can be implemented in a base station or a UE of a cellular communication network depending on whether it is integrated in a downlink (DL) or an uplink (UL) scenario. In each scenario, signaling would be required to integrate the NN-empowered receiver in cellular network, and in each case several benefits can be achieved as summarized in the following.

In downlink transmissions, the NN-receiver needs to be implemented at the UE to compensate for the PA non-linearity at the base station. The UE needs to report its capability to compensate PA non-linearity to the base

station. The base station decides to reduce the PA back-off, considering that out of band emission requirements has to be fulfilled. In this scenario, the proposed method can enhance DL throughput and/or extend the coverage area of the base station. It can improve the energy efficiency of the base station by letting the base station to operate in more non-linear PA operating point in which the PA has higher efficiency. In addition, the requirements on DPD at the base station could be lowered, reducing the complexity of DPD and the required power for digital baseband processing for DPD operations. This would lead to lower heat dissipation at the base station, hence, there would be lower demand on cooling unit (e.g. smaller size of heat sinks), and as a result the size of the base station's radio unit can be reduced.

In uplink transmission, the NN-receiver can be implemented at the base station to perform signal detection in the presence of PA non-linearity of the UE. In this scenario, the UE reports its capability to adapt its PA back-off level to the base station. The base station makes a decision for the UE to increase its output power considering that the out of band emission requirements would be fulfilled, and sends a command to the UE to reduce its PA back-off level. The UE reduces the PA back-off and transmits the signal with higher distortions. The NN-receiver at the base station compensates for the extra distortions and performs signal detection. In this scenario, the uplink throughput and coverage which are usually limited by the quality of the UE hardware can be extended. The proposed method would enable the UE's PA to operate in more non-linear regime which contributes to higher energy efficiency of the UE and increases its battery lifetime.

VII. CONCLUSION

We proposed a neural network empowered receiver to compensate the impact of PA non-linearity of transmitter for DFT-s-OFDM transmitted signals. The proposed receiver is composed of a neural network demapper that is optimized for soft bit computation in the presence of PA non-linearity. We evaluated the performance of the proposed method using link level simulations and compared the performance of the proposed method with that of the legacy receiver in terms of bit error rate (BER), block error rate (BLER), power added efficiency (PAE), and throughput. Our simulation results confirm that the proposed method can partially compensate the impact of distortions due to PA non-linearity of a transmitter and increases throughput and/or extends the coverage of a

communication link. The remaining performance gap for the method to fully compensate the impact of distortions is due to the resource element by resource element processing of the method, where the impact of leakage inter-carrier interference is not compensated for the sake of low complexity processing. Iterative frequency domain equalization (FDE) such as iterative block decision-feedback equalizer (IB-DFE) can be used to enhance equalization and further enhance receiver's performance [12]. Alternatively, the proposed receiver can be used to relax the requirements on inband distortions and the linearization methods to be performed at the transmitter side, and improve the energy efficiency of the transmitter. In particular, the proposed method can be used in uplink communication of a cellular network which is usually coverage limited. Hence, performing linearization techniques at the UE is challenging, and energy efficiency of the UE is desired to increase its battery lifetime. Alternatively, the proposed method can be used in downlink scenario to increase throughput and/or extend the coverage area of the base station, and to enhance the energy efficiency of base stations.

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